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CURRENT PRINCIPLES OF NUTRITIONAL SUPPORT FOR INSULIN-DEPENDENT DIABETES IN CHILDREN. (Literature review)

Abstract:

Type 1 diabetes mellitus is one of the most common chronic endocrine diseases in children, characterized by an absolute insulin deficiency due to autoimmune destruction of pancreatic β -cells. Despite advances in the treatment of type 1 diabetes, a balanced diet is the main component in maintaining stable blood glucose levels, preventing complications and ensuring normal growth and development of the child. The diet of children with diabetes mellitus should be individually tailored, taking into account all nutritional components, and should be adapted to age-related needs and physical activity levels. An important component is the calculation of carbohydrate units, which allows the insulin dose to be adjusted according to the amount of carbohydrates consumed. The diet should also include sufficient protein and healthy fats. It is recommended to include whole grains, vegetables, legumes, low-sugar fruits, nuts, and lean meats in the diet.

Keywords: *type 1 diabetes, children, nutrition, carbohydrates, glycemic index*

Materials and methods: we conducted a review of the current literature based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 10 years. Information on the principles of nutrition for children with type 1 diabetes was analyzed. The data obtained were systematized, analyzed and summarized to form conclusions about the optimal approaches to dietary management of children with type 1 diabetes.

The aim: was to conduct a thorough analysis of current scientific and literary sources concerning the nutritional characteristics of children with type 1 diabetes mellitus, as well as to summarize the results of recent studies in this field. Particular attention was paid to the study of modern principles of diet therapy, the role of a balanced diet in maintaining normoglycaemia, the prevention of complications, and the formation of healthy eating habits in children with this disease. Thus, the work is aimed at identifying and systematizing current approaches to the organization of nutrition in childhood with type 1 diabetes in accordance with modern evidence-based medicine recommendations.

Relevance: Type 1 diabetes in children is a chronic, endocrine, autoimmune disease characterized by the destruction of insulin-producing β -cells in the pancreas. This results in absolute insulin deficiency, leading to impaired carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism. Type 1 diabetes is one of the most common chronic diseases diagnosed in childhood, occurring in 1:400-600 children. An increasing number of young children suffer from type 1 diabetes, with 15-20% of new diagnoses occurring in children under the age of 5 [1].

Despite advances in modern biotechnology and treatment, nutritional therapy remains an important component of diabetes management. Recommendations for a healthy lifestyle are also relevant for children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes [2].

Children with diabetes do not need any restrictive or special diet. Nutritional recommendations for these children are based on the principles of healthy eating that are appropriate for all children [3].

Results and discussion: A balanced diet for children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes has a significant positive effect on their physical and mental development [4].

It is recommended that children with type 1 diabetes have a balanced diet that ensures optimal growth, maintains ideal weight and prevents acute and chronic complications. Approximate energy and nutrient intake should be distributed as follows: carbohydrates 50–55%, fats 30–35% and proteins 10–15%.

Carbohydrates are the main component of nutrition that affects postprandial glycaemia. Carbohydrate intake should not be restricted, as it is necessary for proper growth in children with diabetes mellitus. Adjusting insulin doses according to carbohydrate intake can lead to potential improvements in glycemic control and quality of life [1,2]. Carbohydrate counting is a dietary planning tool for patients with type 1 diabetes mellitus, based on knowledge of foods containing carbohydrates and their effect on blood glucose levels. The required bolus insulin dose is determined based on the total amount of carbohydrates consumed and the insulin-to-carbohydrate ratio [2].

Consumption of sucrose and saturated fatty acids should be limited to 10% of total energy intake. Key nutrition-related challenges are the difficulties in ensuring adequate and varied nutrition in different age groups and conditions, while optimizing glycemic control, achieving adequate micronutrient intake, preventing the consumption of sweetened beverages and unhealthy foods, and developing healthy eating habits [3].

In general, a diet high in protein, lower in saturated fat, and lower on the glycemic index has a positive effect on glycemic control [2].

Studies have shown that common childhood eating habits, such as eating a high glycemic index breakfast (most often sweet cereal with milk), often have a negative impact on glycemic control throughout the day and the following night. However, it can be difficult for children to eat a balanced and nutritious diet on a schedule, as children often have temporary food preferences and food refusal is common even in healthy young children [1].

For example, regarding the principles of nutrition in special camps for children with diabetes, their diet consists of three main meals and three snacks, two of which are between main meals and one before bedtime. Preference is given to nutritious foods with a low glycemic index and high fiber content, namely fruits, vegetables, whole grains, legumes, nuts, and lean protein from poultry and fish. Portion sizes and food types should be individualized for each child or adolescent according to their gender, height, weight, age and level of physical activity. In cases of increased energy loss due to higher levels of physical activity or dehydration, the number of calories should be increased accordingly [2].

Conclusion: Therefore, the diet of children with type 1 diabetes should be balanced, comply with generally accepted principles of healthy eating, and not include strict dietary restrictions. It is also important to

count the carbohydrates consumed at each meal in order to adjust the insulin dose.

References:

1. Streisand R, Monaghan M. Young children with type 1 diabetes: challenges, research, and future directions. *Curr Diab Rep.* 2014;14(9):520. doi: 10.1007/s11892-014-0520-2. PMID: 25009119; PMCID: PMC4113115.

2. Tascini G, Berioli MG, Cerquiglini L, Santi E, Mancini G, Rogari F, Toni G, Esposito S. Carbohydrate Counting in Children and Adolescents with Type 1 Diabetes. *Nutrients.* 2018 Jan 22;10(1):109. doi: 10.3390/nu10010109. PMID: 29361766; PMCID: PMC5793337.

3. Kundu K, Singh P, Seth A. Adherence to Dietary Recommendations in Children With Type 1 Diabetes: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Indian Pediatr.* 2024 Oct 15;61(10):978-982. Epub 2024 Aug 6. PMID: 39113333.

4. Mańkiewicz-Żurawska I, Jarosz-Chobot P. Nutrition of children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes in the recommendations of the Mediterranean diet. *Pediatr Endocrinol Diabetes Metab.* 2019;25(2):74-80. English. doi: 10.5114/pedm.2019.85817. PMID: 31343138.